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Self-assembly synthesis of gallium-doped polymeric carbon nitride/Ti₃C₂ MXene Schottky junction for efficient photosynthesis of hydrogen peroxide

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ABSTRACT

Schottky junction has been widely recognized as one promising strategy for advancing photocatalytic processes, where an internal electric field generated by the Schottky barrier ensures the efficient transfer of charge carriers and enhances the activation capabilities of active sites for reactants, thereby improving solar-to-chemicals performance. However, integration of the Schottky junction into superior photocatalytic H₂O₂ generation remains a formidable challenge. Accordingly, here we present a novel Ga-PCN/Ti₃C₂ Schottky junction, achieved by introducing gallium ions into tri-s-triazine repeating units of PCN and then decorating it with Ti₃C₂ MXene through in-situ electrostatic assembly. Systematic analysis revealed that gallium atoms interlinked with nitrogen in the PCN matrix to construct Ga-N coordination sites, while metallic Ti₃C₂ served as an excellent electron transfer mediator. This configuration simultaneously promoted the separation of photoexcited carriers and shortened charge transport distance from Ga-PCN to Ti₃C₂. As a result, an apparent quantum yield of 1.58 % at 400 nm together with a high H₂O₂ production rate up to 197.6 μmol·g⁻¹·h⁻¹ under visible light irradiation was achieved. This work highlights the synergistic effect between metal atom doping and Schottky junction construction in engineering carbon nitride/MXene-based nanocomposite catalysts for artificial photosynthesis of H₂O₂, providing new insights into the development of advanced high-efficient photocatalysts.

1. Introduction

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), has been widely utilized in various applications in sterilization[1], pharmaceutical[2], and chemical synthesis [3] owing to its intrinsic merits, including the highest active oxygen content (47.1 %w/w) and considerable theoretical output potential (3.0 mega joules (MJ)l⁻¹)[4]. However, conventional industrial methods for H₂O₂ production, e.g., the anthraquinone process [5] and electrolysis [6], suffer from numerous drawbacks including severe energy consumption, generation of toxic by-products and complicated operational procedures. Photocatalysis, a straightforward and environmentally friendly technology that directly converts photon energy into usable chemical energy, with the photocatalyst serving as the central conversion medium[7], has become a major focus of research. The typical H₂O₂ photosynthesis involves either a two-electron oxygen reduction reaction (2 e⁻ ORR) or 2 e⁻ water oxidation reactions (WOR)[8]. However,

achieving light-driven WOR is challenging because of the uphill thermodynamics (1.76 V versus NHE)[9], where the synthesized H₂O₂ tends to decompose under such highly oxidative conditions[9,10]. In contrast, the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) is feasible with photocatalysts that possess a conduction band energy level more negative than the required ORR potential (0.69 V vs. NHE)[11]. Therefore, selectively promoting ORR presents a promising strategy to enhance H₂O₂ photosynthesis.

Polymeric carbon nitride (PCN), a semiconductor carbon nitride conjugated polymer, is recognized as a promising material for next-generation photocatalysts, due to its various advantages[12], such as malleable electronic structure (basic units are triazine ring (C₃N₃) and tri-s-triazine ring/heptazine ring (C₆N₇))[13], excellent chemical and thermal stability (C and N atoms are connected by sp² covalent bonds) and a suitable bandgap (hv < 2.7 eV) for visible light absorption[12,14]. Despite these strengths, rapid recombination of photogenerated charge carriers and a dearth of active sites for ORR hinder its photocatalytic

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efficiency[15]. Therefore, anchoring active sites on photocatalysts to selectively promote ORR presents a promising strategy to enhance H_2O_2 photosynthesis. Several modification methods have been employed to tackle this issue[16]. For instance, doping the alkali metal (Na or K) altered the electronic structure of PCN by building the “ion bridge” between the perpendicular interlayers, thus promoting electron and mass transfer[17]. In addition, coupling PCN with other semiconductor materials to form a Schottky junction is also an alternative option[18]. Density functional theory (DFT) calculations suggest that a built-in electric field is created at the Schottky junction interface[19,20], which regulates the interfacial barrier, promotes electron transfer, and expands the light absorption range[16,18,21], thereby enhancing the selectivity and reaction rate of the catalytic process.

MXenes are a new family member of two-dimensional transition metal carbides, nitrides, and carbonitrides with a general formula $\text{M}_{n+1}\text{X}_n\text{T}_x$ ($n = 1-3$), where M represents a transition metal (such as Ti, Cr, Nb, Sc, Mo, etc.), X denotes carbon or nitrogen, T refers to surface-terminating functional groups (such as $-\text{OH}$, $-\text{O}$, and $-\text{F}$), and x indicates the number of surface groups per formula unit[22,23]. The first reported MXene, $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$, exhibited semimetallic properties as theoretically predicted[23], and has been applied in supercapacitors, rechargeable batteries, and biosensors[24-27], benefiting from their high electrical conductivity, large surface area-to-volume ratio, and the incorporation of redox-active transition metal atoms[24,28]. Recent studies have also demonstrated MXenes’ effectiveness as auxiliary catalysts in enhancing the photocatalytic performance of materials such as TiO_2 [29], black phosphorus (BP)[30], and graphene-based nanosheets[31], which is attributed to MXenes’ lower Fermi energy level and the presence of a Mott-Schottky barrier at the semiconductor-metal interface[29-31], which promotes the separation of photogenerated charge carriers.

In this work, we developed a gallium-doped polymeric carbon nitride (Ga-PCN) photocatalyst through blending calcination, followed by coupling with chemical etched Ti_3C_2 MXene to synthesize a 2D/2D layered Schottky junction composite via electrostatic self-assembly, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Gallium ions present d^{10} electron configuration [15,32], contributing to the formation of the conduction band in semiconductor materials through hybrid sp orbitals with large energy band dispersion, leading to high electron mobility and consequently to enhanced photocatalytic efficiency[15]. Single-atom catalysts (SACs) with a d^{10} electron configuration can precisely regulate the catalytic

reaction pathways and activation energies by adjusting the electronic density of the metal atoms and providing a unique coordination environment[33,34]. The conduction band potential of Ga-PCN moved towards more negative potential in comparison to pure PCN, while the narrowed bandgap extended the range of solar light absorption to an optimized doping ratio, making it ideal for H_2O_2 photogeneration reactions. Upon coupling Ti_3C_2 MXene, the resulting composites exhibited exceptional performance compared to individual components. This study investigates the Schottky barrier effect of two-dimensional MXene, in combination with precise band structure modulation via gallium doping, to achieve efficient spatial separation of photogenerated electron-hole pairs. Moreover, interfacial engineering is employed to enhance light absorption and surface redox kinetics, resulting in a novel photocatalytic system that exhibits both high activity and excellent stability for the green synthesis of hydrogen peroxide.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and reagents

All chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, and all reagents were of analytical grade and were used without further purification. The water used in all experiments was purified through a Milli-Q system (Millipore).

2.2. Synthesis of Ga-PCN

Depending on the synthesis, a specific amount of gallium nitrate was dissolved in ethanol, followed by dispersing 4 g of melamine into the solution. The mixture was ultrasonicated for 60 min to ensure uniform dispersion. The solvent was then removed using a rotary evaporator under vacuum, the obtained white powder was subjected to calcination at a heating speed of $4\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ from 25 to $560\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a tube furnace with a nitrogen atmosphere. The material was maintained at $560\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 h to synthesize gallium ion-dispersed PCN. Pristine PCN was prepared using the same procedure, excluding the addition of the gallium precursor.

2.3. Synthesis of monolayer Ti_3C_2 MXene

The preparation followed a liquid-phase exfoliation method. First, LiF was dispersed in 9 mol L^{-1} concentrated hydrochloric acid and stirred

Fig. 1. Illustration of the fabrication procedure for $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ composites.

for 10 min. Next, 1 g Ti_3AlC_2 powder was slowly added to the acid solution to prevent overheating, and the mixture was stirred for 24 h at a 35 °C water bath. Afterward, the mixture was centrifuged and filtered with deionized water several times until the pH value of the suspension reached 6. The resulting black solution was ultrasonicated in an ice bath for 30 min and then centrifuged at 3500 r/min for 1 h to collect the upper dark green supernatant containing monolayer Ti_3C_2 MXene nanosheets. The concentration of Ti_3C_2 MXene solution was measured as follows: 10 mL of supernatant was transferred to a pre-weighed evaporation dish. After vacuum drying at 40 °C overnight, the final weight was recorded to calculate the concentration.

2.4. Synthesis of Ga-PCN/ Ti_3C_2 MXene heterojunction

The composites were synthesized using a one-step electrostatic self-assembly method. The Ga-PCN powder and Ti_3C_2 nanosheets were mixed in an agate mortar and ground continuously for 30 min until the powder turned light green. The mass ratios of Ti_3C_2 to Ga-PCN were adjusted to 3 %, 5 %, 7 %, and 10 %, respectively. A detailed introduction of composition and naming convention for the experimental catalysts were provided in Table S1.

2.5. Characterization of materials

The morphology of the samples was characterized by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The FESEM images were taken with the FEG-SEM TESCAN S9000G instrument and TEM was conducted by using a Titan Cubed Themis G2 300 electron microscope with a voltage of 300 kV. The microscope features a Schottky emitter as the electron source, providing a resolution of 0.7 nm at 15 keV (In-beam SE). The accelerating voltage can be adjusted from 0.2 to 30 keV. The microanalysis system used is OXFORD – detector Ultim Max – software AZTEC. The elemental composition was analyzed through energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX, Titan 80–300, Philips). Structural features were assessed using powder X-ray diffraction (P-XRD) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR). Thermo Scientific K-Alpha X-ray photoelectron spectrometer (XPS) was used to determine the oxidation states and bonding states of various elements. XPS spectra were obtained through a fixed retarding ratio mode with a bandpass energy of about 20 eV. The operating voltage was set to 12 kV, with Al K α as the X-ray photoelectron source ($h\nu = 1486.6$ eV). Photoluminescence (PL) spectra were recorded with a fluorescence spectrophotometer (RF-6000plus, Shimadzu) using an excitation wavelength (λ_{ex}) of 350 nm[35]. Diffuse reflectance spectra (UV-Vis DRS) were measured using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer (UV-3600plus, Shimadzu), with spectroscopic-grade BaSO_4 as the reference sample. The specific surface area and pore size distribution of the catalysts were determined by nitrogen adsorption-desorption experiments on a Micromeritics ASAP 2460 automated detector, with the samples degassed at 200 °C for 6 h prior to the measurements. Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spintrapping experiments were carried out using an X-band benchtop EPR spectrometer (ADANI's SPINSCAN X). Typical EPR conditions were as follows: sweep width of 12mT and center field at 338mT. DMPO was employed as spin trapping molecule for hydroxyl radical, superoxide and, together with formate, for hole detection. Ex-situ irradiation experiments to monitor the formation of the radicals were performed using an LED with $\lambda \geq 420$ nm. The samples were prepared suspending 10 mg of photocatalyst in i) 0.5 mL of DMPO aqueous solution 0.044 M for the hydroxyl radical detection; ii) 0.5 mL of DMPO solution (0.044 M) in acetonitrile (instead of water to avoid competition with hydroxyl radicals) for the superoxide species; iii) 0.5 mL of aqueous solution buffered at basic pH containing DMPO 0.044 M and sodium formate (0.5 M) for holes detection.[36].

Photoelectrochemical testing was conducted on a CHI-660E electrochemical workstation. The prepared samples were used as the working electrode, while an Ag/AgCl electrode and a platinum sheet

electrode served as the reference and counter electrodes, respectively. A 0.5 mol·L⁻¹ NaSO_4 solution was used as the electrolyte. To prepare the working electrode, ITO glass (3 cm × 1.5 cm) was cut and ultrasonically cleaned sequentially in deionized water, acetone, and ethanol, sequentially. 5 mg of the synthesized catalyst was dissolved in 1 mL of a solvent mixture (water/IPA volume ratio of 3:1). Subsequently, 10 μL of Nafion solution was added, and the mixture was thoroughly ground to form a slurry, then coated onto the ITO glass (effective area: 2.25 cm²) and dried at 60 °C for 20 min. Transient photocurrent measurements were carried out using a 300 W xenon lamp (CEL-PF300-T8) as the light source, turning on and off the lamp at intervals of 20 s with a starting voltage of 0.5 eV[37]. The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were performed with a frequency sweep ranging from 100 kHz to 0.01 Hz[38].

2.6. Density functional theory calculations (DFT)

Spin-polarized first-principles calculations based on the DFT + U method were conducted using the VASP package[39]. Specifically, the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) functional was used in conjunction with the Hubbard U correction ($U = 4.5$ eV) to account for electron-electron exchange correlation interactions. The plane-wave energy cutoff was set at 500 eV, with a force convergence criterion of 0.02 eV/Å[40]. A k-point grid of $2 \times 2 \times 1$ was employed, and the energy convergence criterion for the geometric structure optimization was set at 1×10^{-6} eV.

2.7. Photocatalytic reaction towards H_2O_2 production

Twenty milligrams of the catalyst were added to a sealed glass bottle containing a mixture of 36 mL water and 4 mL sacrificial reagent (10 % vol. ethanol, methanol, or triethanolamine). Pure O_2 gas was bubbled into the bottle for 30 min. A 500 W xenon lamp equipped with a cutoff $\lambda > 420$ nm provides the simulated solar light, while the solution is magnetically stirred for 5 h. At fixed time intervals, 2 mL of the liquid is taken to measure the concentration of H_2O_2 using the colorimetric method within a PACKTEST kit (WAK- H_2O_2 from Kyoritsu Chemical-Check Laboratory Corp.). The concentration of H_2O_2 was determined using a digital PACKTEST spectrometer (model ED723 from GL Sciences Inc.).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Morphology and structural characterization

TEM and SEM were utilized to visualize the microstructure and morphology of the prepared catalysts. Pure PCN exhibited a porous, wrinkled nanosheet-stacked morphology (Fig. 2a), which implies that its surface can offer anchoring sites for immobilizing active metals. The morphological characteristics of Ga-PCN showed no significant difference from PCN (Fig. S1a), indicating the loading of Ga species did not alter the interconnected nanosheet structure of PCN. Elemental mapping confirmed a uniform distribution of C, N, O, and Ga across the surface of the Ga-PCN catalyst (Fig. S1g). Notably, numerous small black dots were observed in the HRTEM images (Fig. S1e), with no additional crystalline phases detected (Fig. S1f), which means that Ga exists as highly dispersed atomic clusters on the carbon nitride support[15]. The surface of the Ti_3C_2 MXene nanosheets appeared smooth and homogeneous (Fig. S1b), suggesting that the prepared MXene was not oxidized. TEM and HRTEM images of the Ga-PCN/ Ti_3C_2 composite revealed a distinct layered interlinking structure with complex Moiré patterns and clear boundary differentiation, indicating the multilayered morphology is a result of stacking multilayered PCN onto Ti_3C_2 MXene nanosheets through intermolecular Van der Waals forces (Fig. 2d-e)[41], which is consistent with presented SEM photograph (Fig. 2b). The layered nature and atomic ordering of Ga-PCN/ Ti_3C_2 layers were further confirmed by selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern (Fig. 2e), where the

Fig. 2. (a) SEM image of PCN and (b) $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{-5\%}$, (c) EDX spectra and corresponding overlay element (inset) of $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{-5\%}$, (d) TEM image, (e) HRTEM image, and (f) SEAD pattern of $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{-5\%}$, (g) Elemental mapping figure of C, Ga, N, O and Ti in $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{-5\%}$, respectively.

hexagonally-arranged atomic structure can be identified at the outermost layer.

The porosity of synthesized catalysts was investigated through low-temperature N_2 adsorption/desorption measurements. All samples exhibited a type IV isotherm with H_3 -type hysteresis loops in the $P/P_0 = 0.5\text{--}1.0$ region [42], reflecting the mesoporous structure of the catalysts (Fig. S2a). Furthermore, the presented Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) pore size distribution revealed that the pore sizes were mainly distributed in the 1–10 nm range (Fig. S2b). This nano-scale slit-like internal pore structure is thought to arise primarily from the stacking of nanosheets. However, the BJH Desorption average pore diameter of $\text{Ga-PCN}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ MXene decreased down to 11.91 nm compared to that of $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}$ (12.61 nm), likely due to the dense stacking of Ti_3C_2 MXene nanosheets in the composite, which partially covers the surface pores of Ga-PCN .

The crystal structure of materials was analyzed by XRD measurement. Both bare PCN and the Ga-PCN samples exhibited two prominent X-ray diffraction peaks at approximately 13.2° and 27.8° , assigned to the inter-layer structural packing of the tri-s-triazine rings (100) and interplanar stacking of the aromatic units (002) [33], respectively (Fig. 3a-b). In comparison, the crystal peaks belonging to the Ga-PCN were slightly wider than those of PCN, and the intensity of the diffraction peak at 13.1° weakened (Fig. 3a), indicating reduced crystallinity and in-plane periodicity in PCN due to the addition of Ga. Besides, the (002) crystal planes in Ga-PCN shifted toward the high-angle direction, suggesting the

narrower interlayer spacing after Ga doping, which is consistent with the SEM figures and is favorable for exciton migration between layers. In contrast, the (002) planes of pure Ti_3C_2 MXene shifted toward the low-angle direction, which is attributed to the exfoliation of stacked sheets via HF etching. The absence of a peak at about 39° , corresponding to the (104) plane of Ti_3AlC_2 (Fig. S3a), confirms the complete removal of Al layers in Ti_3AlC_2 . Notably, the $\text{Ga-PCN}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ MXene composite retained the characteristic (002) diffraction peaks of Ti_3C_2 , with peak intensity increasing as the Ti_3C_2 content increased in the PCN matrix, indicating the successful incorporation of Ti_3C_2 MXene phase into PCN structure. The slight shift in the (002) diffraction peak position observed in the composite may be attributed to electronic structure adjustments within the catalyst.

Steady-state PL emission spectroscopy was utilized to assess the ability of photocatalysts to separate charge carriers. The photoluminescence of semiconductor materials primarily arises from the recombination rate of internal photogenerated electrons and holes [43]. As shown in Fig. S3b, the PL intensity at a typical wavelength of 467 nm remarkably decreased with increasing gallium doping, indicating that the addition of gallium ions enhances electron separation in PCN. However, excessive gallium did not further contribute to reducing the PL intensity. Furthermore, the $\text{Ga-PCN}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ MXene composites exhibited a lower PL intensity than Ga-PCN , attributed to the superior electrical conductivity of Ti_3C_2 MXene (Fig. 3c). Despite that, the redundancy

Fig. 3. (a) XRD patterns of PCN and Ga-PCN samples, (b) XRD patterns of Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene-X%, (c) steady-state photoluminescence spectra of Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene-X%, (d) time-resolved PL spectra of PCN, Ga₁₀-PCN and Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene-5% and average fluorescence lifetime (inset).

MXene led to the disorderliness and agglomeration of the composites, which negatively impacted charge carrier migration. In addition, the dynamics of photogenerated carriers in excited states of catalyst were investigated by time-resolved PL spectra (Fig. 3d). Compared with the average fluorescence lifetime (τ_{Ave}) of 14.15 ns for PCN, Ga₁₀-PCN and Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene-5% showed shorter excited state existence time, with lifetimes of 13.27 and 11.13 ns, respectively (Table S2). This phenomenon can be explained by the Ga-N interaction formed within the PCN system, anchored by gallium single atoms (details on the Ga-N interaction were further discussed in the XPS section). This interaction creates a specific non-radiative electron transfer pathway between the Ga site and the electron-donor carbon nitride. Besides, the gallium single atom site can act as an electron acceptor, thereby enhancing the photocatalytic activity.

XPS analysis provided the full region element spectrum of catalysts and the individual element spectra for C 1s, N 1s, Ti 2p, and Ga 2p, elucidating the chemical state of the interplay between isolated metal sites and the PCN skeleton, as well as the intricate interactions between Ga-PCN and Ti₃C₂ MXene. The binding energies of the four emerged photoelectron peaks in the Ga-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene spectrum correspond to C, N, Ti, O, and Ga, respectively (Fig. S4). Among these, the O element signal likely arises from oxygen-containing functional groups on the carbon nitride surface or surface-adsorbed oxygen. The peak located in the C 1s orbital spectrum of PCN and Ga-PCN around 288.1 eV and 284.6 eV is in accordance with the binding energies of N-C=N and surface adsorbed carbon (C-CO₂)[44], respectively (Fig. 4a). No apparent new peak appeared, suggesting the metal atom doping preserves the chemical states of carbon in PCN and the interaction between Ga and C is nearly negligible. For the composite, the disappearance of C-Ti bonds at 282.2 eV associated with MXene, and the increased intensity of C-C bonds compared to Ga-PCN, suggests that the formation of composites is driven by strong C-C covalent bond interactions. The N 1s

diagrams are displayed in Fig. 4b. The two prominent peaks at 398.6 eV and 400.5 eV correspond to N-(C)₃ and C=N-C bonds[45], respectively. In particular, a distinct nitrogen peak potentially associated with the N-metal bond appeared near 398.3 eV, and its slight shift toward higher binding energy direction after MXene loading may be attributed to the change of local atomic configuration and coordination environment of anchored Ga species. The Ti 2p spectra of single Ti₃C₂ MXene showed in the Fig. 4c can be divided into six peaks at 455.9 eV, 457.0 eV, 459.5 eV, 461.6 eV, 463.0 eV, and 465.1 eV, corresponding to Ti-C 2p_{3/2}, Ti-O 2p_{3/2}, Ti(III) 2p_{1/2}, Ti-C 2p_{1/2}, Ti-O 2p_{1/2} and Ti-O 2p_{5/2}[46], respectively. After the formation of the composite, the Ti-C bond positions moved towards lower binding energies (454.5 eV for Ti-C 2p_{3/2} and 460.5 eV for Ti-C 2p_{1/2}). This highlights the presence of chemical bonding interaction and the formation of a built-in electric field between the PCN and MXene[18,46], rather than a simple physical-connected compound, the electrons were transferred from Ga-PCN to the MXene surface. In the deconvoluted Ga 2p spectrum, the peak found at 1118.2 eV was identified as the characteristic Ga-N bond and it is worth noting that the MXene did not affect the coordination of the doped Ga atoms (Fig. 4d). Thus, based on prior theoretical studies that the PCN framework can develop two-dimensional planar pores populated with six nitrogen lone electron pairs, it can be inferred that Ga atoms in PCN tend to form a coordinated structure with surrounding N atoms[15,16].

3.2. Photo-electrochemical properties

The study of band structure provides crucial insights into the light absorption range and bandgap energy of the semiconductor materials, allowing for the determination of the relative energy levels of the conduction bands (CB) and valence bands (VB)[44]. This, in turn, helps reveal the influence of Ga single-atom incorporation on the system's electronic configuration and the delocalization of photogenerated

Fig. 4. High-resolution XPS spectra of pristine PCN, Ga₁₀-PCN, Ti₃C₂ MXene and Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene –5%: (a) C 1 s, (b) N 1 s, (c) Ti 2p and (d) Ga 2p.

charge carriers. UV–Vis DRS spectra given in Fig. 5(a) revealed that all prepared catalysts absorb strongly to the UV-A region (315 nm < λ < 400 nm), Ga atoms doping caused slightly redshift in the absorption edges of Ga-PCN samples compared to the pristine PCN, this probably due to Ga ions altering the intrinsic orbital distribution of the planar C-N network, enhancing the delocalized π -electrons and varying degrees of bandgap transitions. Likewise, the composite showed better light absorption performance owing to the metallic properties of MXene with outstanding harvesting capabilities (Fig. 5b). Bandgap energies were calculated from the tangent of the Kubelka-Munk function to the square root of the photon energy. According to Tauc plot formula[47]:

$$(\alpha h\nu)^{1/n} = B(h\nu - E_g) \quad (1)$$

where α is the absorbance, h is the Planck constant (6.62×10^{-34} J·s), and ν is the light frequency, the value of n is taken as 1/2 for PCN-based samples. The observed reduction in the bandgap of Ga-PCN is related to the formation of Ga-N bonds, which also facilitates the rapid transfer of electrons after the catalyst absorbs light energy (Fig. S5a). Furthermore, the incorporation of MXene formed a well-structured conductive network framework, promoting the efficient separation of photo-generated electron-hole pairs, leading to more effective utilization of solar energy (Fig. S5b), and contributing to improved photocatalytic performance.

Mott-Schottky curve provides information about the type of semiconductor and identifies the locations of the band potential for the

samples. As demonstrated in Fig. 5c-d and Figs. S5a-b, the tangential positive slope observed in all the Mott-Schottky curves represents the typical characteristics of n-type semiconductors for the synthesized PCN-based catalysts. The flat band potential of the Ga-PCN samples measured under the Ag/AgCl electrode was summarized in Figs. S6-S7. For intuitive comparison, all values were further converted to potential relative to the normal hydrogen electrode (NHE)[48]:

$$E_{NHE} = E_{Ag/AgCl} + E_{Ag/AgCl}^0 \quad (2)$$

Conduction band (E_{CB}) and valence band (E_{VB}) under normal hydrogen electrode (NHE, pH = 7) are calculated by[48,49]:

$$E_{CB} = E_{Ag/AgCl} - E_{Ag/AgCl}^0 + 0.059 \cdot pH \quad (3)$$

$$E_{VB} = E_{CB} + E_g \quad (4)$$

The standard electrode potential $E_{Ag/AgCl}^0$ at pH 7 is 0.197 V[50]. The unsaturated edge-constrained Ga-CN system demonstrates a more negative conduction band position, indicating that the non-uniform coordination of Ga in the Ga-CN system effectively modulates the electronic configuration of the support, thereby improving the effective separation and transfer of charge carriers. All the catalysts exhibited sufficient reduction potentials to facilitate the generation of H₂O₂ from oxygen (ORR).

Transient photocurrent response and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) were applied to evaluate the carrier migration

Fig. 5. (a) UV-Vis DRS spectra of pristine PCN and Ga₁₀-PCN, (b) UV-Vis DRS spectra of Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene-X%, (c) Mott-Schottky plots of PCN and (d) Ga₁₀-PCN, (e) Transient photocurrent curves of PCN, Ga₁₀-PCN, and Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene-X%, (f) EIS plots of pristine PCN, Ga₁₀-PCN, and Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene-X%.

efficiency and dynamic electrochemical processes of the samples. As illustrated in Fig. S5c, the transient photocurrent responses of Ga₁₀-PCN exhibited a higher photocurrent density compared to pure PCN, indicating that the incorporation of Ga single atoms promotes the separation of photogenerated electron-hole pairs within the catalyst system, consistent with PL and UV-Vis DRS results. Moreover, Ga-PCN demonstrated smaller arc radii than pure-phase PCN in the EIS test (Fig. S5d), suggesting lower impedance in these systems, which leads to higher charge carrier migration efficiency. As a result, more electrons can be effectively involved in the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR). However, an excess of Ga ions does not yield further EIS performance enhancement (Fig. S5d). This suggests that the unsaturated edge-clustered Ga single atoms with heterogeneous coordination patterns, isolated and coexisting on the surface, show a better photoelectrochemical response. MXene functionalized as a co-catalyst, leading to further improvements in photoelectrochemical performance by enhancing the dynamic migration of carriers and improving charge carrier utilization efficiency, ultimately benefiting photocatalytic hydrogen peroxide production. It is noteworthy that the photoelectrochemical properties of the composite system do not increase proportionally with the MXene loading. Despite the highest loading amount in Ga-PCN/Ti₃C₂-10 %, it exhibits weaker photocurrent density and larger impedance compared to Ga-PCN/Ti₃C₂-5 % and Ga-PCN (Fig. 5e-f). This finding further confirms that the agglomeration of MXene at the carbon nitride edges is detrimental to the separation and transfer of photogenerated electron-hole pairs.

3.3. Evaluation of photocatalytic H₂O₂ production

H₂O₂ photosynthesis was carried out in a batch reactor as illustrated in Fig. S8. Initially, the impact of varying gallium ion doping concentrations on photocatalytic H₂O₂ production was investigated. Pristine PCN showed negligible catalytic activity. Among the Ga-doped PCN samples, both Ga₇-PCN and Ga₁₀-PCN exhibited the highest H₂O₂ generation efficiency in the solution containing ethanol as a sacrificial agent at pH value 7, reaching approximately 3.5 times that of undoped PCN (Fig. S9). Therefore, the intrinsic catalytic activity of each catalyst was further evaluated by conducting parallel experiments without a sacrificial agent. The concentration of H₂O₂ produced by Ga₁₀-PCN after 5 h

was 1.58 times and almost 9 times higher than that of Ga₇-PCN and pure PCN, respectively (Fig. 6a), indicating that optimal gallium content in Ga-PCN for photocatalytic H₂O₂ production is 10 mmol of Ga(NO₃)₃ in 4 g of PCN). In addition, the composites with MXene contents ranging from 3 %-10 % were prepared and tested the photocatalytic activity under identical conditions. The amounts of H₂O₂ produced after 5 h of visible light irradiation were given in Fig. 6b. It is evident that the addition of Ti₃C₂ MXene remarkably improved the photocatalytic performance compared to that of bare Ga₁₀-PCN. Notably, the composite with a 5 % MXene content exhibited the highest H₂O₂ production (16.6 mg L⁻¹, which can also be converted to 197.6 μmol·g⁻¹·h⁻¹). However, further increases in MXene content resulted in a gradual decline in H₂O₂ production efficiency, which might be attributed to the fact that increasing opacity of the co-catalyst (dark green-colored Ti₃C₂ MXene) obstructs light absorption as well as to the chemical heterogeneity and interfacial effects induced by the coexistence of large-area two-dimensional materials.

To investigate the intermediate species involved in photocatalytic H₂O₂ reactions, a series of radical quenching experiments were performed. Various scavengers, including p-benzoquinone (p-BQ, 1 mM), t-Butanol (TBA, 1 mM), and EDTA (1 mM) were added to the mixture to selectively scavenge superoxide radicals (·O₂), hydroxyl radicals (·OH), and electrons (e⁻), respectively. As shown in Fig. 6c and Fig. S10, the addition of TBA and EDTA made minimal impact on H₂O₂ production, indicating that ·OH is not the primary reactive species in the reaction. Based on the VB potential of Ga₁₀-PCN, it can be inferred that the composite photocatalyst cannot oxidize water to generate H₂O₂. However, the addition of p-BQ completely suppressed the H₂O₂ yield, proving that ·O₂ is the inevitable intermediate for H₂O₂ synthesis. These results demonstrated that photocatalytic H₂O₂ generation in the system primarily occurs through a sequential two-step single-electron indirect pathway (O₂ → ·O₂ → H₂O₂) rather than the direct two-electron O₂ reduction route (O₂ → H₂O₂), in which the photoexcited electrons are captured by O₂ to form ·O₂ as a crucial intermediate.

Cycling experiments were carried out under identical conditions to assess the reproducibility and structural stability of catalysts (Fig. 6d). The concentration of H₂O₂ remained virtually consistent over three cycles, suggesting that the composite catalyst has excellent stability.

Fig. 6. (a) Amounts of H₂O₂ produced from Ga-PCN without ethanol, (b) Photocatalytic H₂O₂ production activities of Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene, (c) Effect of different scavengers on the concentration of photocatalytic H₂O₂ concentration; (d) Photochemical stability of Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene-5%.

Compared with the H₂O₂ production ability of previously published PCN-based catalysts, Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene showed higher photocatalytic activity, suggesting that metal ions doping and Schottky junction construction are effective strategies for enhancing the photocatalytic performance of carbon nitride (Table 1).

Subsequently, we examined the reaction conditions to optimize the H₂O₂ production process. The action spectra of H₂O₂ under different monochromatic light irradiation and their UV-Vis DRS dates were presented in Fig. 7 and Fig. S11 simultaneously. Apparent quantum

Table 1
Comparison of photocatalytic H₂O₂ generation performance with various photocatalysts.

Photocatalyst	Solvent system	Light Source	H ₂ O ₂ production (μmol·g ⁻¹ ·h ⁻¹)	Ref.
Defective PCN	H ₂ O: IPA (2:1)	λ > 420 nm	96	[51]
Mesoporous PCN	H ₂ O: EtOH (9:1)	λ > 420 nm	83.5	[52]
Ti ₃ C ₂ MXene/Porous PCN	H ₂ O: IPA (9:1)	λ > 400 nm	131.71	[16]
TiO ₂ /Ti ₃ C ₂ MXene/Au	H ₂ O: EtOH (9:1)	360 nm < λ < 380 nm	100	[53]
WO ₃ /Ti ₃ C ₂ MXene/Au	H ₂ O: EtOH (9:1)	λ > 420 nm	110.5	[54]
P-doped PCN	H ₂ O (100 mL)	λ > 420 nm	174	[55]
PCN/PDI	H ₂ O (100 mL)	λ > 400 nm	21.08	[56]
Ag@U-PCN-NS	H ₂ O (100 mL)	λ > 420 nm	67.5	[57]
Honeycomb-like-PCN	H ₂ O: IPA (8:1)	λ > 420 nm	96.80	[58]
Ga-PCN/Ti ₃ C ₂ MXene	H ₂ O: EtOH (9:1)	λ > 420 nm	197.6	This work

Fig. 7. Action spectrum and adsorption spectra of PCN, Ga₁₀-PCN, and Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene-5% under irradiation at wavelengths of 400 nm, 420 nm, 450 nm, and 470 nm.

efficiency (AQY) is a principal parameter for evaluating the light utilization efficiency of photocatalysts[59] and was calculated using various light bandpass filters with wavelengths of 400 ± 10 nm, 420 ± 10 nm, 450 ± 10 nm and 470 ± 10 nm[44].

$$AQY(\%) = \frac{[N_A \times h \times c] \times [nH_2O_2 \times 2]}{I \times S \times t \times \lambda} \quad (5)$$

Among these, N_A represents Avogadro's constant, h is the Planck constant, c is the speed of light, nH₂O₂ refers to the amount of generated

H_2O_2 . S is the illuminated area, and I is the light intensity entering the reactor, measured by using an optical power meter. t represents the total irradiation duration, and λ denotes the wavelength of the monochromatic light. As summarized in Table S3, the variation in H_2O_2 concentration is consistent with the absorption spectra of the catalysts, which means that the catalytic reaction was driven by light excitation. The AQY at 400 nm for $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ MXene-5 % composite reached up to 1.58 %, almost 2.89 and 1.40 times higher than that of PCN and $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}$, respectively. In particular, the photocatalytic activity persisted even when the wavelength was expanded to 470 nm, demonstrating excellent visible-light responsiveness.

The reaction conditions were systematically investigated to optimize the photocatalytic H_2O_2 generation using the $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ MXene-5 % composite. Ethanol was selected hole sacrificial agent in Fig. S12a. Keeping the same volume, the catalytic reaction with 10 % ethanol as the sacrificial agent showed the best performance, with H_2O_2 yields 1.31 times and 6 times higher than those of the methanol and water systems, respectively. In contrast, the existence of triethanolamine (TAA) resulted in severe inhibition consequences that the yielded H_2O_2 concentration was lower than 0.5 mg L^{-1} . This finding can be explained by the more negative redox potential of ethanol (-0.197 V versus NHE) compared to TAA (0.656 V vs. NHE), which means ethanol more effectively consumes holes at a rate, thereby preserving photogenerated electrons for participation in the reaction [15]. Moreover, the significant alkaline nature of TAA in aqueous solutions may lead to proton quenching, disrupting the acid-based balance. To further explore this, the effect of pH on photocatalytic H_2O_2 production was studied and the experimental results were presented in Fig. S12b. When the solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid, H_2O_2 generation significantly increased at pH 3 compared to. However, when sodium hydroxide was added, causing the pH to rise from 7 to 9, the H_2O_2 concentration decreased sharply. This is due to the self-decomposition of H_2O_2 in alkaline solutions, where it is difficult to maintain stability. Considering that, lower pH conditions are favorable for enhancing the H_2O_2 production efficiency. Additionally, the effect of different gas atmospheres (oxygen, nitrogen and compressed air) bubbled into the solution before light irradiation was investigated to verify the formation pathway of H_2O_2 . It was observed that the concentration of generated H_2O_2 in air is only about half that in pure oxygen (Fig. S12c), while negligible amounts were produced in a nitrogen atmosphere. These results indicate that high-purity oxygen gas is essential for the photocatalytic H_2O_2 generation process, which primarily occurs through the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR).

The final concentration of produced H_2O_2 is determined by the interplay between its formation and decomposition rates on the catalyst surface, reflecting a dynamic equilibrium process. To better understand the underlying principles from a kinetic perspective, appropriate kinetics models were utilized to describe the behavior of H_2O_2 in-situ formation and decomposition. Specifically, the formation rate (K_f , $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) adheres to zero-order kinetics, while the decomposition rate (K_d , min^{-1}) follows first-order kinetics [53,60]. The change in H_2O_2 concentration as a function of time (t) can be summarized as follows [53]:

$$[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2] = K_f/K_d(1 - \exp(-K_d t)) \quad (6)$$

Comparing the resulting K_f and K_d values shown in Fig. 8, it is evident that the H_2O_2 generation rate constant of the $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}$ material was 3.48 times higher than that of the original PCN. Likewise, the generation rate further improved with the incorporation of MXene, proving the synergistic catalytic effects of MXene as a co-catalyst and its crucial role in the junction. However, the H_2O_2 decomposition rate constants also increased accordingly. This phenomenon may be associated with the secondary separation of photogenerated carriers, which minimizes their interaction with the generated H_2O_2 to a certain extent, thereby consequently accelerating decomposition. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that the increase in H_2O_2 generation rate was even more pronounced at a

Fig. 8. Formation rate constant (K_f) and decomposition rate constant (K_d) for H_2O_2 production.

pH of 3, while the decomposition rate constant decreased compared to neutral conditions. This suggests that the abundant H^+ ions in an acidic solution play a crucial role as essential reactants in the H_2O_2 production process, favoring the forward reaction while simultaneously suppressing its decomposition, contributing to higher overall yields. Detailed evidence supporting this observation will be discussed in the subsequent section.

3.4. Photocatalytic mechanism

In the existence of 5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline N-oxide (DMPO) as a radical trapper, EPR spectroscopy was employed to monitor the reactive redox species generated during the photocatalytic reaction, providing more evidence for the H_2O_2 generation pathway. As demonstrated in Fig. 9a, four distinct $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ signals appeared in the EPR spectrum of $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{-5\%}$ after 5 min of visible light irradiation with the intensity gradually increasing over time. In contrast, no evident $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{OH}^{\cdot}$ or $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{h}^+$ signal can be observed after 30 min of irradiation, as shown in Fig. 7b-c. These results suggest that O_2 was reduced by photogenerated electrons to form $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ due to their enough reduction potential, confirming that $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ is a crucial and indispensable intermediate in photocatalytic H_2O_2 production, which is in good accordance with the results of previous sacrificial agent experiment (Fig. 6c). Moreover, the signal intensity of $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ of Ti_3C_2 -decorated $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}$ was about three times stronger than that of $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}$ and pure PCN (Fig. 9d), demonstrating that the H_2O_2 generation process is photoinduced, and coupling of Ti_3C_2 MXene efficiently promoted $\text{Ga}\text{-PCN}$ to produce more $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ under light irradiation, leading to superior photocatalytic activity. Interestingly, $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{h}^+$ signals were only detectable in the EPR spectrum of $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}$, while not in those of PCN or $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{-5\%}$ (Fig. 9f). This suggests that the incorporation of Ga atoms accelerated the generation of charge carriers, thus leading to an accumulation of h^+ in the VB of $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}$. Reported studies have confirmed that H_2O_2 is an efficient hole scavenger [61] ($\text{h}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{OH}^{\cdot} + \text{H}^+$). However, the absence of a $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{OH}^{\cdot}$ signal in the EPR spectrum of $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}$ revealed that no OH^{\cdot} is formed because of the weak oxidation potential of holes (Fig. 9e), further demonstrating that the generation of H_2O_2 is a sequential ORR process rather than WOR reaction. Besides, the intensity of $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ signals in the EPR spectrum of both PCN and $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}$ decreased after 15 min of irradiation (Fig. S13), suggesting a reduction in $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ concentration. Conversely, the $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ signals exhibited by $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-PCN}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{-5\%}$ remained stable over 30 min, indicating improved catalytic stability

Fig. 9. EPR spectra of Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂-5%: (a) DMPO·O₂·, (b) DMPO·OH· and (c) DMPO·COO·h⁺ at 0 (dark), 5, 15, and 30 min of light irradiation. Comparison of the EPR signal intensity of used catalysts in this study: (e) DMPO·O₂·, (d) DMPO·OH· and (f) DMPO·COO·h⁺.

and durability.

The interfacial interactions and electronic structure between Ga₁₀-PCN and Ti₃C₂ were theoretically analyzed by Density Functional Theory (DFT) to reveal the electronic distribution and bonding at the interface impact charge transfer mechanisms. Theoretical band gap and densities of states (DOS) of the PCN, Ga-PCN and Ti₃C₂ MXene were

displayed in Fig. 10a-c, respectively. Obviously, Ti₃C₂ exhibited metallic properties without a direct/indirect band gap (Fig. 10a). The theoretical bandgap of PCN and Ga₁₀-PCN were calculated as 1.21 eV and 0.92 eV, respectively, which are obviously smaller than the experimentally observed values. It is a consequence of the fact that DFT calculation usually underestimates the energy gaps for its own limitation[62].

Fig. 10. Adsorption band gap diagram (left) and total state density (right) of (a) Ti₃C₂, (b) PCN, (c) Ga-PCN. Work function (Φ) of (d) Ti₃C₂ MXene (001), (e) PCN, (f) Ga-PCN (111), and the optimized geometrical structure model (inset). The blue and red dashed lines represent the Vacuum level and Fermi energy level, respectively.

Additionally, the total DOS distribution revealed that the valence band maximum of both PCN and Ga₁₀-PCN is predominantly composed of N 2p orbitals, whereas the conduction band minimum is formed by contributions from both C 2p and N 2p orbitals (Fig. 10a-b), which means that Ga atoms do not participate in the band edge structure. Evidently, Ga-PCN not only exhibited a narrower band gap compared to pure PCN, but its VB and CB also shifted upward relative to those of pure PCN. This result indicates a favorable alteration in the electronic structure and enhanced redox ability. Therefore, although Ga atoms are not involved in the information of band edge structure, they influence the band gap and the band edge position by donating and transferring electrons within PCN as intuitively reflected by charge density difference ($\Delta\rho$) in Fig. 11. Work function (Φ) is a crucial parameter for evaluating electron transfer capabilities in materials. A lower work function indicates that less energy is required to eject an electron into the vacuum, implying the material's higher tendency to donate electrons[63]. This has an inverse relationship with the Fermi energy level. As illustrated in Fig. 10e-f, the computed respective work functions of PCN and Ga-PCN Ti₃C₂ are 5.268 eV and 3.518 eV, respectively. This significant attenuation suggests that the Fermi level of Ga-PCN is higher than that of PCN, arising from the contribution of gallium's unique D¹⁰ electron configuration, making the valence electrons in PCN more easily excitable. Furthermore, Ti₃C₂ possessed the highest work functions of 5.826 eV (Fig. 10d). Therefore, it can be deduced that as the two layers of Ga-PCN/Ti₃C₂ incorporate, the Fermi level difference drives electron transfer from Ga-PCN to Ti₃C₂ until an equilibrium is achieved.

Fig. 11a-b presented the three-dimensional and planar-averaged charge density difference of Ga₁₀-PCN, respectively. The results clearly revealed that the interfacial monodispersed gallium atoms formed chemical bonds with four surrounding nitrogen atoms, establishing

stable interfacial interactions, while electrons are transferred to the adjacent carbon atoms, leading to strong electron transfer. This process constructed a hybrid electronic structure between the Ga atoms and carbon nitride (CN). Further observation of the charge density difference of the Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂ composite revealed that charge accumulation and depletion are principally distributed in the interlayer space, which sufficiently disclosed the strong interfacial interaction. Correspondingly, the electrons from Ga₁₀-PCN are transferred to Ti₃C₂ MXene, in line with work function results, which convincingly demonstrated that an interfacial built-in electric field was constructed (Fig. 11d), which aids in the migration of photogenerated charge carriers.

In light of the experimental findings and theoretical analysis, the mechanism behind enhanced photocatalytic H₂O₂ generation in Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene composite was proposed. As illustrated in Fig. 11d and Fig. 12. Initially, under visible light irradiation, photoinduced electrons were transferred from the valence band (VB) of Ga₁₀-PCN to the conduction band (CB), and then quickly migrated to the Ga atoms with strong electron capture ability through the robust interfacial interactions. The increased electron density around Ga atoms causes a shift in the Fermi level of Ga₁₀-PCN in a more negative direction. Subsequently, the electrons transferred to the Ti₃C₂ MXene due to its lower Fermi level to achieve an equilibrium state upon contact. An interfacial built-in electric field thus was created, forcing the upward bending of the energy band in Ga₁₀-PCN and inducing the formation of the Schottky barrier (Φ_{SB}), preventing the electrons trapped by Ti₃C₂ from flowing back to CB of Ga₁₀-PCN as a result, which realized the highly efficient charge separation. Consequently, a Schottky-junction structure was constructed between Ga₁₀-PCN and Ti₃C₂ MXene. Notably, electrons reacted with dissolved O₂ in water, driving the ORR process to generate hydrogen peroxide. The enhanced photocatalytic H₂O₂ evolution

Fig. 11. (a) Three-dimensional and (b) planar-averaged charge density difference of Ga-PCN, (c) electron charge density distribution of Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂-5%. Note: the yellow and blue areas represent electron accumulation and consumption, respectively. (d) Schematic diagram of the interface interaction between Ga₁₀-PCN and Ti₃C₂ MXene.

Fig. 12. Schematic diagram of photocatalytic hydrogen peroxide generation mechanism of Ga₁₀-PCN/Ti₃C₂-5% Schottky-junction.

activity can be ascribed to the ideal gallium-atomic sites and the Schottky-junction formation, both of which promote the transfer and separation of photogenerated charge carriers, resulting in superior performance in H₂O₂ generation.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, a gallium-doped polymeric carbon nitride decorated with Ti₃C₂ MXene (Ga-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene) Schottky-junction photocatalyst was successfully fabricated through blending calcination of gallium precursor and pure PCN, followed by direct mixing of Ga-PCN with prepared Ti₃C₂ MXene nanosheet at different mass ratios. The photocatalytic activity of optimum gallium doping (10 mmol) and MXene loading (5 wt%) achieved the highest visible-light H₂O₂-yield rate of 197.6 μmol·g⁻¹·h⁻¹ with an AQY at 400 nm of 1.58 %, which is almost 1.7-folded than Ga₁₀-PCN and 6.4-folded than pure PCN, respectively, significantly surpassing the efficiency of other photocatalyst based on PCN. Comprehensive characterization results combined with DFT calculations demonstrated that Ga-N sites in the Ga-PCN facilitated the transfer of photoinduced charge carriers and the H₂O₂ generation pathway in the mixture of H₂O and O₂ is two-electron ORR. Furthermore, the enhanced H₂O₂ generation performance under visible light irradiation can be attributed to the intimate 2D/2D interfacial contact and the formation of the Schottky junction, which provides an effective transmission channel for charge redistribution and leads to better separation of photoexcited carriers. This work highlights the feasibility of artificial designing various efficient intercalated photocatalysts based on carbon nitride materials and MXenes, offering promising prospects for energy-related applications as well as environmental remediation.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jingbo Ni: Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Vittorio Boffa:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Xiaoyu Sun:** Methodology, Data curation. **Teruhisa Ohno:** Supervision, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Lorenzo Sarasino:** Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Maria Cristina Paganini:** Visualization, Validation. **Paola Calza:** Resources, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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